

OPEN GOVERNMENT DATA (OGD) IN EUROPEAN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS CURRICULUM: CURRENT STATE AND PROSPECTS

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It is everybody's knowledge now that Open Government Data (OGD) pertains to the availability of datasets pertaining to government operations and functioning via license-free formats (Afful-Dadzie and Afful-Dadzie, 2017) and these datasets are linked with different themes contingent upon the area of administration like energy, education, climate, tourism, environment, infrastructure, etc. (Ubaldi, 2013). Governments have been benchmarking their OGD initiatives across standard indices like ODIN, OKFN, Open Data Barometer, etc. (Lnenicka et al., 2022; Lnenicka and Nikiforova, 2021) and ample research exists on assessing the quality of OGD portals from the demand (i.e. the governments' efforts at maintaining the quality of datasets) and supply (i.e. the perceptions of users regarding the quality of datasets) side (Crusoe et al., 2019; de Souza et al., 2022; Islam et al., 2021; Kaasenbrood et al., 2015; Khurshid et al., 2022; Lnenicka et al., 2022; Purwanto et al., 2020; Saxena and Janssen, 2017; Shehata and Elgllab, 2021; Talukder et al., 2019; Weerakkody et al., 2017; Wirtz et al., 2016; Wirtz et al., 2018; Wirtz et al., 2019; Zuiderwijk et al., 2015). Given the magnitude of academic interest on OGD- especially in the last 10 years- it remains to be assessed as to how far has the domain progressed in the academic environs and surprisingly, no research has been conducted to elucidate the infusion of this very significant domain- that is relatable to the extent to which the governments are forwarding their claims regarding the furtherance of transparent and corruption-free administration apart from bolstering citizen participation, collaboration and trust (Gil-Garcia et al., 2020; Hellberg and Hedstrom, 2015) besides serving as a means for value creation and innovation by a range of stakeholders (Jetzek et al., 2012; Jetzek et al., 2014) - in the diverse platforms that are meant for furthering academic dialogue and discussion.

Research pertaining to meta-analysis and reviews of the OGD-focused studies already published in academic publication outlets is well-acknowledged (Attard et al., 2015; Kalampokis et al., 2011; Safarov et al., 2017; Wirtz et al., 2022; Wirtz and Birkmeyer, 2015) and to carry forward the baton of OGD-focused research, the present study aims to establish the current baseline of European OGD curricula and describe their fundamental aspects.

The authors applied text analytics and systematic secondary data review methods to explore the nature and scope of existing OGD European study programs to draw a European OGD education current state and prospects. In order to address this aim, this study examines four research questions: R1) What is the current educational offer of the OGD study programs in the top 200 European Universities? R2) What fields of study are the SSC study programs covering? R3) What competencies characterize each cluster of the OGD study programs? R4) What are the common and diverging features of such clusters?

The search for the OGD study programs includes the definition of two types of keyword terms lists and combinations of them. The search combines two types of terms. The first type covered the subject (e.g., OGD). These keywords were searched in the titles and descriptions of the programs. Second, we defined the keywords that characterize training/educational degrees (e.g., MSc). The search combined one term of the subject group and one of the training/educational group (e.g., OGD AND MSc). The terms for search by subject are Open AND Government AND Data, Open AND Data, Open AND Government, Open AND e-Government OR eGovernment), Data AND Management, Government OR e-Government OR eGovernment AND Data, Data AND Reuse, Data AND Analytics AND Government. The terms for search by institutional/educational degree are Bachelor, Capacity Building, Certificate, Continuing Professional Education, Diploma, Education, Executive Master, Graduate, Higher Education, Master, MSc, PhD, Program, Specialization, Training, Undergraduate, Joint Master, MOOC. Google search engine was the main search source. Only English-language search results with geographical location Europe were accepted. Websites of European higher education organizations (public and private) and institutes have been analyzed. Having selected the programs for inclusion in the study, we compiled a database with information derived from their web pages: the program description (program name, the academic level, the aims of the program and/or learning goals, the area of program specialization, competencies, admission requirements); program content (course name, the course type, the course description, the course credits, the learning outcome/goals, course URL); additional information about the institution (name of the institution, the country of the institution, the institution type) and programs (e.g. degree title, the credits-ECTS, the teaching method, the program cost, the program duration, the program URL).

A threefold approach to study the topic was used: (1) text analytics methods (such as text pre-processing, Topic modelling (LDA), Cosine similarity, Elbow and Gap Statistic Methods and the k-means clustering algorithms) to identify OGD educational programs curriculum clusters based on program titles and course description; (2) expert knowledge to review and refine the results against program objectives, descriptions and modules, and also contextual competencies coding and grouping; and (3) statistical analysis to process metadata collected and the results summarization (Ciesielska. et al., 2021).

In total, we identified 21 courses and 5 programs from European Universities and eleven online courses delivered via EdX, Coursera, and MOOCs. As an OGD educational programs curriculum analysis, we identified three clusters: 1) Open Data for Policymakers (30%); 2) Open Data and Digital Transformation (15%); 3) Open and Smart Government (5%); 4) Data Analytics for Government (50%). Each cluster covers specific, non-repetitive content and contains study programs at three levels: supplementary, bachelor and master. We identified 53 unique OGD competencies. The most frequent of them were assigned to the educational programs clusters. The

analysis revealed significant differences in the characteristics of each of identified OGD educational programs clusters, which concern both (i) formal features, such as the use of different teaching methods and program duration, and (ii) conceptual ones, such as lack of consistency in defining roles, responsibilities, competencies and skills to effectively meet the needs of OGD training and imbalances in the interdisciplinary structure of the course/program.

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